

PILOTE SITES: GEOPOLYMERS APPLICATION

Benedictine Monastery (Catania, Sicily)

Università di Catania

MORTARS APPLICATION

Application of mortars for repair deteriorated masonry

CONSOLIDANTS APPLICATION

Application of consolidants for restoration of deteriorated masonry

TILES REPRODUCTION

Maiolica tiles of the Caffeaos in the Eastern Cloister

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TESSERAE REPRODUCTION

Reproduction of a portion of the Roman Domus pavement

Cefalù Cathedral (Palermo, Sicily)

Application of mosaics tesserae for replacement interventions of compromised original elements